

Small molecule screening *in vivo* for discovery of medicines to treat autism.

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We describe here a method for discovery of medicines to treat autism and autism spectrum disorders involving the use of functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to capture activation of specific regions associated with animation or sociability.

Citations

1. Borsook, D., Becerra, L. and Hargreaves, R., 2006. A role for fMRI in optimizing CNS drug development. *Nature reviews Drug discovery*, 5(5), pp.411-425.

2. Ramot, A., Taschbach, F.H., Yang, Y.C., Hu, Y., Chen, Q., Morales, B.C., Wang, X.C., Wu, A., Tye, K.M., Benna, M.K. and Komiyama, T., 2025. Motor learning refines thalamic influence on motor cortex. *Nature*, 643(8072), pp.725-734.

3. Peelen, M.V., Wiggett, A.J. and Downing, P.E., 2006. Patterns of fMRI activity dissociate overlapping functional brain areas that respond to biological motion. *Neuron*, 49(6), pp.815-822.

4. Beauchamp, M.S., Lee, K.E., Haxby, J.V. and Martin, A., 2003. FMRI responses to video and point-light displays of moving humans and manipulable objects. *Journal of cognitive neuroscience*, 15(7), pp.991-1001.

5. Koshino, H., Carpenter, P.A., Minshew, N.J., Cherkassky, V.L., Keller, T.A. and Just, M.A., 2005. Functional connectivity in an fMRI working memory task in high-functioning autism. *Neuroimage*, 24(3), pp.810-821.

6. Silani, G., Bird, G., Brindley, R., Singer, T., Frith, C. and Frith, U., 2008. Levels of emotional awareness and autism: an fMRI study. *Social neuroscience*, 3(2), pp.97-112.

7. Giansanti, D., 2023. An Umbrella Review of the Fusion of fMRI and AI in Autism. *Diagnostics*, 13(23), p.3552.

8. Gomot, M., Bernard, F.A., Davis, M.H., Belmonte, M.K., Ashwin, C., Bullmore, E.T. and Baron-Cohen, S., 2006. Change detection in children with autism: an auditory event-related fMRI study. *Neuroimage*, 29(2), pp.475-484.

9. Shao, L., Fu, C., You, Y. and Fu, D., 2021. Classification of ASD based on fMRI data with deep learning. *Cognitive Neurodynamics*, 15(6), pp.961-974.

10. Lee, R.J., Coccaro, E.F., Cremers, H., McCarron, R., Lu, S.F., Brownstein, M.J. and Simon, N.G., 2013. A novel V1a receptor antagonist blocks vasopressin-induced changes in the CNS response to emotional stimuli: an fMRI study. *Frontiers in systems neuroscience*, 7, p.100.